

Impact of Jio Network Service among the Customers - A Study on with Special Reference to Dharmapuri District

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Abstract

Indian telecom Industry, largest growing industry, has massive potential to serve people and improving day by day. The number of mobile phone subscribers in the country would exceed 50 million by 2010 and cross 300 million by 2016. The Reliance JIO network has created a significant impact on the working of the telecom industries. There are of a lot of new entrants in the telecom sector. The JIO network, on the whole, has been able to satisfy the customers and reduce the mobile expenses of the users to an affordable level when compared to the scenario before the entry of the network in the telecom sector. The various statistical tools applied in the study such as Percentage Analysis, Mean, Standard Deviation, Chi-Square, T-Test and ANOVA analysis. This study only focused on Dharmapuri District. The respondents involved are having lack of time to respond to all questions and haste responses have also been provided for some questions. The present paper attempts an analytical of Impact of Jio Network service among the Customers A Study on With Special Reference to Dharmapuri District.

Keywords: LFY Smartphone, Jio Apps, Digital Currency, Jio net Wi-Fi, Telia Company.

Introduction

After the globalization of India economy in 1991, the telecommunication sector remained one of the most happening sectors in India. The recent year’s witnesses rapid and dramatic changes in the field of telecommunications. In the last few years more and more companies both foreign, domestic, come into cellular service, service market and offers a large number of services to the people. A consumer may be referred to anyone engaged in evaluating, acquiring, using or disposing of services which he expects will satisfy his wants.

Indian telecom Industry, largest growing industry, has massive potential to serve people and improving day by day. With awareness in a young generation about this sector, the public demand is all time high and still increasing. With upgradation in technology and demand, all major services providers from across the world entered in this sector. The government also makes liberal policies to facilitate investors and also setup a fair and proactive regulatory framework.

Telecom sector is expected to generate 4 million direct and indirect jobs in next five years. The employment opportunities to be created due to increases in market size in rural areas.

The number of mobile phone subscribers in the country would exceed 50 million by 2010 and cross 300 million by 2016, according to Cellular Operators Association of India (COAI).

Commercial Launch

The company commercially launched its services on 5 September 2016. Within the first month, Jio announced that it had acquired 16 million subscribers. This is the fastest ramp-up by any mobile network operator anywhere in the world. Jio crossed 50 million subscriber mark in 83 days since its launch, subsequently crossing 100 million subscribers on 22 February 2017. By October 2017 it had about 130 million subscribers.

Reliance Jio

Reliance JioInfocom Limited announced the launch of its digital services with JIO in Mumbai on 1st September 2016 with Jio Welcome Offer. With the permission of Telecom Regulatory Authority of India, users will have access to unlimited LTE data and national voice, video, messaging services, Jio applications, and content, free of cost up to 31 December 2016.

Reliance JIO Vision

1. The best quality broadband network with the highest capacity;
2. A world of affordable, cutting-edge devices;
3. Compelling applications and content;
4. Superior digital service experiences;
5. Affordable and simple tariffs.

Jio 4G Broadband

Jio 4G Broadband is one of the game-changers. The destructive idea that RJIL has proposed, has shaken the market. With Jio 4G broadband, people may be able to access high-speed broadband for as low as Rs. 50 per GB. With 2300 Hz spectrum for 4G all over India- 22 circles, and 800Hz and 1800Hz spectrum for 4G in 10 and six circles respectively, Jio has it all covered.

The licenses are valid till 2035. With 250,000 km of fiber network across the country, it is supposed to be the fastest and the widest network with least data drop. With JionetWiFi, it can be used to transmit WiFi in homes and offices at affordable prices.

LYF Smartphones

Jio had earlier tied up with Intex for providing handsets with 4G VoLTE technology all over the country. They manufactured several models low on cost and high on features- ready for the next level of 4G and voice telephony. However, they soon decided to launch their own brand of phones. They named the range as Lyf phones. The names have been consistent with the models such as Water 1, Water 2, Flame 1, Flame 2, Wind, Earth, among others. At present, the company offers more than 15 handsets with a varying range of features. They are mostly made in China phones repackaged as Lyf phones. They come with a Jio preview offer, before September 5, the only way to get access to a JioSim.

Jio Apps

Jio Apps- announced free till 2017, are one of the major ideas of investment of RJIL. At present, the following apps are available in beta phase only for Jiosim users (although anyone can download, it requires Jiosim to use them),

- Jio TV – live TV services
- Jio Cinema – just like Netflix, a video library.
- Jio Music – music player and subscription model.
- Jio Join- Volte Phone Simulator
- JioMags- Magazine reader and subscriptions
- Jio Xpress News – News and daily events
- Jio Security – Security app
- Jio Drive Cloud storage app
- Jio Money Wallet – like PAYTM and Airtel money.

Review of Literature

The review of literature explains the various studies that are carried out in the field of research that is related to the current research. There are various national and international studies in the areas of the telecom sector. The various studies that are carried out in the sector are surveyed to arrive at the research gap of the study. The research gap will help to frame the research design of the study. The research gap outlines the border within which the research is going to be carried out. The research gap that is the mainstay of the research is arrived based on the literature survey.

Importance of the Study

The Reliance JIO network has created a significant impact on the working of the telecom industries. The working of the new industries will affect the existing industries. The policies, offers and other activities will significantly have an impact on the sector. The introduction of the JIO network has already created a lot of debt burden on the other industries operating in the telecom sector. There are a lot of new schemes and promotions that have been implemented by the new industries. It has cut the cost of the mobile expenses of the users. The assessment of the awareness and satisfaction level of the users will prove to be good for the working of the industries thereby creating an impact on the expenses of the users. This will also lead to improvement in the plans and increasing the usages of the network by the potential users.

Statement of the Problem

There are of a lot of new entrants in the telecom sector. The telecom sector is having the burden of high operating costs in the recent decades. The auctioning of the bands, building infrastructure, manpower requirement, etc. are the major problems in the sector. The problems in the telecom sector are proving to be a burden for the existing industries. The new entrants are having a lot of problems to handle in the telecom sector. The introduction of the new companies in the sector will either directly or indirectly affect the working of the whole sector. The introduction of the JIO has altogether changed the dimensions of the sector in the country. The survival of any company is based on the awareness and satisfaction level of the consumers. There are assessment problems when it comes to studying the awareness and working of the new companies in operational means. The current study involves the problem of assessing the awareness and satisfaction level of the users of the JIO network.

Objectives of the Study

- To examine the level of awareness about the services of the JIO network among the users.
- To analysis the usage of the JIO network and its effectiveness among the users of the network.
- To assess the satisfaction level of the users of the JIO network.
- To identify the various problems faced by the users of the JIO network.

Research Methodology

Research Design

The research design explains the nature and design of the research that is to be undertaken to solve the research problem. There are various types of research which are adopted based on the nature of the problem that is selected for the study. The research design explains the tools that are to be adopted based on the nature of the problem. The current research is both descriptive and exploratory. The descriptive nature of the study explains the description of the characteristics of the population involved in the study. The relationship between the demographic variables and dependent variables is also assessed by describing the nature of the variables.

The exploratory research is adopted to identify the various new criteria related to the field of research. The new criteria are to be identified based on the course of the study and methodology adopted. It explores the various research variables that are new to the area based on the study design.

Sampling Design

The sampling works as the representative part of the population. The representative part is selected based on some of the scientific manner. The sampling of the study constitutes the units that are selected from the population of the study. The sampling acts as the representation of the population and the study of the sample will provide solutions which can be inferred to the whole population. The sampling that is to be adopted for the current study is one of the methods of non-probability sampling. The adoption of non-random sampling is the absence of a list of the total number of the members involved in the study. The sampling technique of convenience sampling is considered appropriate and it is adopted for the current study. The number of samples selected for the study is 190 in Dharmapuri District for Jio network user.

Area and Period of Study

The area of the study for the current research is selected in Dharmapuri District. The period of study for the research is from January 2018 to July 2018.

Statistical tools to be Used

The statistical tools are necessary to create a relationship between the variables of the study which help to attain the objectives of the study. The various statistical tools applied in the study such as Percentage Analysis, Mean, Standard Deviation, Chi-Square, T-Test and ANOVA analysis.

The scope of the Study

The main aim of the study is to assess the level of awareness and satisfaction in the Dharmapuri district. It also aims at finding out the effectiveness of the Jio network among the users in the District. The border of the study is well defined and it works in the mindset of the consumers of the telecom products. This will help to improve the quality of the service provided by the network that is under consideration for the study.

Limitations of the Study

The study has only carried out on the limited scale due to the financial constraints. The users of the network have been somewhat biased due to the offers and promotions. This study only focused on Dharmapuri District. The respondents involved are having lack of time to respond to all questions and haste responses have also been provided for some questions.

Factors Influencing the Selection of Jio Network Services

The identify the various factor influencing the selection of JIO network services is the primary objectives of the study. There are six factors that were selected to know the influencing capacity of the factors. The assessment of the various factors is done with the help of the one sample t-test which is explained in the following part.

Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant relationship between various factors influencing the selection of the JIO network services

H1: There is the significant relationship between various factors influencing the selection of the JIO network services

Table 1 One – Sample t-test – Factors influencing the selection of JIO Network Services

S. No	Network Service	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
1	Call Charges/Tariff Plans	4.12	0.76	0.06	20.21	189	0.000**
2	Network Service Available	4.30	0.84	0.06	21.29	189	0.000**
3	Customer Care Service	4.00	0.83	0.06	16.62	189	0.000**
4	Offer and Schemes	3.87	1.08	0.08	11.10	189	0.000**
5	Recommended by Friends	3.83	0.97	0.07	11.76	189	0.000**
6	Connectivity	1.40	0.49	0.04	-44.90	189	0.000**

(** indicates p-value is significant at 1% level, * indicates p-value is significant at 5% level)

The above table explains the various factors that are influencing the selection of the JIO network services. Based on the results the null hypothesis was rejected for all the variables of the study. The users of the JIO network is influenced by Call Charges/Tariff Plans, Network Service Available, Customer Care Service, Offer and Schemes, Recommended by Friends and Connectivity where the p-values are significant at one percent level. Hence it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between various factors influencing the selection of the JIO network services.

Satisfaction Level of JIO Network Services

The assessment of the satisfaction level of JIO network services is the primary objectives of the study. There are various variables that are used to assess the satisfaction level of the variables. The assessment of the satisfaction level of the variables is done with the help of the one sample t-test which is explained in the following part.

Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant relationship between satisfaction levels of users of JIO network services

H1: There is a significant relationship between satisfaction levels of users of JIO network services

Table 2 One – Sample T-test – Satisfaction Level of JIO network services

S. No	Network Service	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
1	Calling Quality	4.17	0.94	0.07	17.30	189.00	0.000**
2	Network Availability	3.84	1.09	0.08	10.63	189.00	0.000**
3	Data Connection	3.76	1.13	0.08	9.33	189.00	0.000**
4	Price	3.82	1.25	0.09	8.98	189.00	0.000**
5	Availability	2.23	1.12	0.08	-9.48	189.00	0.000**
6	Customer Care	1.53	0.56	0.04	-36.13	189.00	0.000**

(** indicates p-value is significant at 1% level, * indicates p-value is significant at 5% level)

The above table explains the satisfaction levels of users of JIO network services. Based on the results the null hypothesis was rejected for all the variables of the study. The users of the JIO network is satisfied with the calling quality, network availability, data connection, price, availability and customer care where the p-values are significant at one percent level. Hence it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between the variables of the satisfaction level of the users of the JIO network services.

The Relationship among Educational Qualification and Satisfaction Level of JIO users

The relationship among the educational qualification and satisfaction level of JIO users is identified with the help of the ANOVA test. The educational qualification is classified into five categories and its relationship among the various factors of satisfaction level is tested.

Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant difference among educational qualification concerning satisfaction level of JIO users

H1: There is a significant difference among educational qualification concerning satisfaction level of JIO users

Table 3 ANOVA - Educational Qualification and Satisfaction Level of JIO users

S. No	Education Qualification / Satisfaction level	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Between Groups	14.86	4.00	3.71	4.57	0.002**
	Groups	150.41	185.00	0.81		
	Total	165.27	189.00			
2	Between Groups	12.39	4.00	3.10	2.69	0.032*
	Groups	212.87	185.00	1.15		
	Total	225.26	189.00			
3	Between Groups	19.35	4.00	4.84	4.05	0.004**
	Groups	220.99	185.00	1.20		
	Total	240.34	189.00			

4	Price	Between Groups	21.27	4.00	5.32	3.57	0.008**
		Groups	275.28	185.00	1.49		
		Total	296.55	189.00			
5	Availability	Between Groups	8.21	4.00	2.05	1.67	0.159
		Groups	227.61	185.00	1.23		
		Total	235.81	189.00			
6	Customer Care	Between Groups	2.08	4.00	0.52	1.69	0.155
		Groups	57.23	185.00	0.31		
		Total	59.31	189.00			

(** indicates p-value is significant at 1% level, * indicates p-value is significant at 5% level)

The results of the ANOVA reveal that satisfaction level of calling quality (0.002), data connection (0.004) and Price (0.008) are significantly differing based on the educational qualification of the respondents. The p-values of these variables are statistically significant at the 1 percent level.

The variable of network availability is statistically significant at the 5 percent level. Hence it also has difference based on the educational qualification of the respondents. The variables of availability (0.159) and customer care (0.155) have not found any significant difference based on the educational qualification of the respondents. The p-values are not statistically significant and the null hypothesis of these variables is rejected.

The Relationship among Owning 4G Handset and Factors Influencing the Selection of JIO Network

The relationship among the owning 4G Handset and age factors influencing the selection of JIO network is identified with the help of the ANOVA test. The owning of 4G Handset is classified into two categories and its relationship among the age factors influencing the selection of JIO network is tested. The following results were arrived at

Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant difference among Owning 4G Handset concerning age factors influencing the selection of JIO network

H1: There is a significant difference among Owning 4G Handset concerning factors age influencing selection of JIO network

Table 4 ANOVA - 4G Handset and Factors Influencing the Selection of JIO Network

S. No	Education Qualification / Satisfaction level	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Call Charges/ Tariff Plans	Between Groups	1.06	1.00	1.06	1.84	0.176
		Groups	108.39	188.00	0.58		
		Total	109.45	189.00			
2	Network Service Available	Between Groups	0.10	1.00	0.10	0.14	0.707
		Groups	133.80	188.00	0.71		
		Total	133.90	189.00			

3	Customer Care	Between Groups	3.29	1.00	3.29	4.88	0.028*
		Service	126.71	188.00	0.67		
		Total	130.00	189.00			
4	Offer and Schemes	Between Groups	1.23	1.00	1.23	1.06	0.305
		Groups	218.48	188.00	1.16		
		Total	219.71	189.00			
5	Recommended by Friends	Between Groups	0.75	1.00	0.75	0.80	0.372
		Groups	176.52	188.00	0.94		
		Total	177.27	189.00			
6	Connectivity	Between Groups	2.67	1.00	2.67	11.67	0.001**
		Groups	42.94	188.00	0.23		
		Total	45.60	189.00			

(** indicates p-value is significant at 1% level, * indicates p-value is significant at 5% level)

The results of the ANOVA reveal that factors that are influencing based on the owning of the 4G handset is connectivity which is statistically significant at 1 percent level and customer care service which is statistically significant at 5 percent level. These factors are having significant influence created by owning 4G Handset. The factors of Call charges, network service availability, offers and Schemes and recommended by friends are not statistically significant. Therefore it can be concluded there is no significant difference among Owning 4G Handset concerning these factors influencing the selection of JIO network.

The relationship among Annual Income and Factors Influencing the Selection of JIO Network

The relationship among the annual income and factors influencing the selection of JIO network is identified with the help of the ANOVA test. The annual income is classified into five categories and its relationship among the various factors influencing the selection of JIO network is tested. The following results were arrived at

Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant difference among annual income concerning factors influencing the selection of JIO network

H1: There is a significant difference among annual income concerning factors influencing the selection of JIO network.

Table 5 ANOVA- Annual Income and Factors Influencing the Selection of JIO Network

S. No	Education Qualification / Satisfaction level	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Call Charges/ Tariff Plans	Between Groups	2.95	4.00	0.74	1.28	0.279
		Groups	106.51	185.00	0.58		
		Total	109.45	189.00			
2	Network Service Available	Between Groups	10.60	4.00	2.65	3.98	0.004**
		Groups	123.30	185.00	0.67		
		Total	133.90	189.00			

3	Customer Care	Between Groups	2.16	4.00	0.54	0.78	0.538
		Service	127.84	185.00	0.69		
		Total	130.00	189.00			
4	Offer and Schemes	Between Groups	3.40	4.00	0.85	0.73	0.575
		Groups	216.31	185.00	1.17		
		Total	219.71	189.00			
5	Recommended by Friends	Between Groups	16.01	4.00	4.00	4.59	0.001**
		Groups	161.26	185.00	0.87		
		Total	177.27	189.00			
6	Connectivity	Between Groups	1.94	4.00	0.48	2.05	0.089
		Groups	43.66	185.00	0.24		
		Total	45.60	189.00			

(** indicates p-value is significant at 1% level, * indicates p-value is significant at 5% level)

The results of the ANOVA reveal that factors that are influencing based on the annual income are network service available and recommended by friends which is statistically significant at 1 percent level. These factors are having significant influence created by annual income. The factors of Call charges, customer care service, offers and Schemes and connectivity are not statistically significant. Therefore it can be concluded there is no significant difference among annual income concerning these factors influencing the selection of JIO network.

Association between Marital Status and Return to Reliance JIO

The marital status of the respondents has a strong association with the selection of the network and switching of the network based on the various offers and schemes. The following tests the association between marital status and return to reliance JIO using the Chi-square test.

Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant association between marital status and return to reliance JIO network

H1: There is a significant association between marital status and return to reliance JIO network

Table 6 Cross Table - Marital Status and Return to Reliance JIO

		Return to Reliance Jio		Total
		Yes	No	
Marital Status	Married	22	24	46
	Unmarried	99	45	144
	Total	121	69	190

The cross table reveals that majority of the unmarried have opted that they will return to reliance JIO in future. The response of the married persons reveals that more or less the same distribution among the yes and no option.

Association between Annual Income and Features of Reliance JIO

The annual income of the respondents determines the expenses that can be incurred towards the mobile expenses of the family. The following tests the association between annual income and features of reliance JIO using the Chi-square test.

Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant association between annual income and features of reliance JIO

H1: There is a significant association between annual income and features of reliance JIO

Table 8 Cross Table - Annual Income and Features of Reliance JIO

Annual Income		A Feature of Reliance Jio				Total
		Conne Activity	Free Schemes	Advertise elements	Good will	
Annual Income	Below Rs. 10,000	35	7	16	10	68
	Rs.10,001- Rs. 20,000	59	7	11	0	77
	20,001-30,000	17	0	4	3	24
	30,001-40,000	10	1	5	0	16
	Above Rs. 40,000	3	2	0	0	5
	Total	124	17	36	13	190

All categories of the annual income of the respondents reveal that the connectivity has primary importance and it is a most attractive feature among the others. The other features have got least responses when compared to the connectivity feature of the Reliance JIO network.

Association between Having Mobile Phone and Features of Reliance JIO

The availability of the compatible mobile phone is needed to use any of the SIM cards. The mobile phones can influence the usage of the cards based on the configuration. The following tests the association between having mobile phone and features of Reliance JIO using the Chi-square test.

Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant association between having mobile phone and features of reliance JIO

H1: There is a significant association between having mobile phone and features of reliance JIO

Table 10 Cross Table - Having Mobile Phone and Features of Reliance JIO

Having Mobile		A feature of Reliance JIO				Total
		Connectivity	Free Schemes	Advertisements	Goodwill	
Having Mobile	Yes	109	15	32	13	169
Phone	No	15	2	4	0	21
	Total	124	17	36	13	190

The cross-tabulation reveals that there is a strong association between having a mobile phone and features of the reliance JIO. The majority of the respondents having the mobile phone have responded that the features of the reliance JIO influence them. The primary factor that influences is the connectivity of the network.

Association between Annual Income and Reasons for Selection of Reliance JIO

The annual income of the respondents plays a vital role in the selection of the mobile network based on the various expenditure calculations. The following tests the association between annual income and reasons for selection of reliance JIO using the Chi-square test.

Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant association between annual income and reasons for selection of reliance JIO

H1: There is a significant association between annual income and reasons for selection of reliance JIO

Table 12 Cross Table - Annual Income and Reasons for Selection of Reliance JIO

Annual Income		Reason for Selection of Reliance Jio		Total
		Unlimited Calling Services	Unlimited Data Services	
Annual Income	Below Rs. 10,000	45	23	68
	Rs.10,001- Rs.20,000	59	18	77
	20,001-30,000	12	12	24
	30,001-40,000	13	3	16
	Above Rs. 40,000	5	0	5
	Total	134	56	190

The cross-tabulation of the variables reveals that the majority of the respondents have opted for unlimited calling services when compared to the data services of the network. All the categories of the annual income have majorly selected unlimited calling services.

Table 13 Chi-Square Table - Annual Income and Reasons for Selection of Reliance JIO

S. No	Annual Income	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
1	Pearson Chi-Square	9.835a	4	0.043*
2	Likelihood Ratio	10.931	4	
3	Linear-by-Linear Association	.825	1	
4	N of Valid Cases	190		

(** indicates p-value is significant at 1% level, * indicates p-value is significant at 5% level)

This chi-square test reveals that there is an association between annual income and reasons for selection of reliance JIO. The p-value of the test is statistically significant at the five percent level. Therefore it can be concluded that annual income of the respondents has an association with reasons for selection of reliance JIO network.

Association between Place of Living and Type of Connection

The place of living has a choice of selection to have which type of connection based on the coverage of the network in the area. The following tests the association between place of living and type of connection using the Chi-square test.

Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant association between place of living and type of connection

H1: There is a significant association between place of living and type of connection

Table 14 Cross Table - Place of Living and Type of Connection

Place of Living		Type of Connection		Total
		Prepaid	Postpaid	
Place of Living	Rural	54	20	74
	Semi-Urban	35	55	90
	Urban	15	11	26
	Total	104	86	190

The cross-tabulation reveals the distribution of the respondents based on the place of living to different types of connection the respondents opt for. The majority of the respondents are having prepaid connection whereas the semi-urban area people have a postpaid connection.

Association between Services Liked by the Users and Using Reliance Jio

The users are attracted by the various types of services offered by the network. The usage of the Reliance JIO can be attributed to the various factors. The following tests the association between services liked by the users and using reliance JIO with the help of Chi-square test.

Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant association between services liked by the users and using reliance JIO

H1: There is a significant association between services liked by the users and using reliance JIO

Table 16 Cross Table - Services liked by the Users and Using Reliance Jio

Cross Table - Services liked by the Users and Using Reliance JIO		Using Reliance Jio		Total
		Yes	No	
Service you like the most	Data Services	73	54	127
	Call Rates	17	11	28
	Network Coverage	26	9	35
	Total	116	74	190

The responses reveal that the various services used by the users on the majority have selected data services for the usage of the reliance JIO. The other services also on the majority like by the users. The various services offered help in the development of the usage of the reliance JIO.

Table 17 Chi-Square Table - Services liked by the Users and Using Reliance JIO

S.No	Chi- Square Table - Services liked by the Users and Using Reliance JIO	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
1	Pearson Chi-Square	3.260a	2	0.196
2	Likelihood Ratio	3.405	2	
3	Linear-by-Linear Association	2.994		
4	N of Valid Cases	190		

(** indicates p-value is significant at 1% level, * indicates p-value is significant at 5% level)

This chi-square test reveals that there is no association between services liked by the users and using Reliance JIO. The p-value of the test is not statistically significant. Therefore it can be concluded that services liked by the users on t have any impact on the usage of the reliance JIO.

Association between Having Mobile Phone and Services you Like the Most

The usage of the mobile phone is based only on the liked services that are used by the respondents. The following tests the association between having mobile phone and services you like the most

Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant association between having mobile phone and services you like the most

H1: There is a significant association between having mobile phone and services you like the most

Table 18 Cross Table – Having Mobile Phone and Service You Like Most

Having a Mobile Phone	Service you like the Most			Total
	Data Services	Call Rates	Network Coverage	
Yes	116	26	27	169
No	11	2	8	21
Total	127	28	35	190

The service most liked by the people having the mobile phone on the majority is the data services. The users have like all the services provided by the network on the majority when compared to the no responses.

Table 19 Chi-Square Table - Having Mobile Phone and Service You Like Most

S. No	Having Mobile Phone	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
1	Pearson Chi- Square	6.135a	2	0.047*
2	Likelihood Ratio	5.219	2	
3	Linear-by- Linear Association	4.427	1	
4	N of Valid Cases	190		

(** indicates p-value is significant at 1% level, * indicates p-value is significant at 5% level)

This chi-square test reveals that there is an association between marital status and return to reliance JIO network. The p-value of the test is statistically significant at the five percent level. Therefore it can be concluded that having a mobile phone is associated with the service liked most and data services most liked by all the respondents.

Findings

- The analysis and interpretation of the study help to identify the major findings of the study about the objectives of the study. The following part explains the major findings of the study
- The gender classification has an equal distribution of both male and female where the male is slightly higher than female.
- The majority of the respondents involved in the study are unmarried.
- The Educational qualification of the respondents reveals that most of the respondents involved in the study are educated.
- There is majority 89 percent of the respondents own 4G Handset and least category of no has 11.10 percent of the respondents about the 4G Handset.

- The Jio oriented LYF handset is not majorly used by the respondent involved in the study which has been not used by the majority of 70 percent and used by least category of 30 percent.
- The majority of the respondents have revealed that the knowledge of the JIO network has been attained through advertisement with 45.80 percent and least is from publicity with 17.40 percent.
- The respondents of the study have said that the company is having good connectivity which is opted by 65.30 percent of the respondents and lowest category is goodwill with 6.80 percent.
- The reason behind the selection of JIO network is found that they provide unlimited calling with 70.50 percent and least category is unlimited data services with 29.50 percent.
- The majority of 60.50 percent of the respondents were found to have satisfied with the services of the JIO network and 39.50 percent of the respondents are not satisfied with the JIO network.
- The majority of 56.30 percent of the respondents were revealed that there should be an improvement in the network coverage of the JIO network whereas others feel that it should remove calling congestion which is supported by 43.70 percent.
- The respondents of the study reveal that the introduction of the JIO has provided stiff competition to the other industries in the telecom sector which is supported by 51.10 percent and least category of switching of customers is having the support of 11.60 percent.
- The responses reveal the respondents are satisfied with the plans, network, data speed and calling quality of the Reliance JIO.
- The responses reveal the respondents are satisfied with the network
- Availability, price, availability and customer care given by the Reliance JIo.
- The problems reveal that the network issue is found to be the prominent problem.
- The overall performance of the JIO network is average which is revealed by the responses of the respondents.
- The responses of the study reveal that the respondents are satisfied with the data call charges of Reliance JIO.
- The users of the JIO network is influenced by Call Charges/Tariff Plans, Network Service Available, Customer Care Service, Offer and Schemes, Recommended by Friends and Connectivity
- The users of the JIO network is influenced by Call Charges/Tariff Plans, Network Service Available, Customer Care Service, Offer and Schemes, Recommended by Friends and Connectivity
- The educational qualification of the respondents feels that the availability and customer care of the JIO network have to be improved to influence the users in selecting the network.
- The factors of Call charges, network service availability, offers and Schemes and recommended by friends is not influencing the owners of 4G Handset to use JIO.
- The factors of Call charges, customer care service, offers and Schemes and connectivity of the JIO network is not influencing the users based on the annual income of the respondents of the study
- The annual income has primary influence based on the feature of Reliance JIO in the selection of the network.

Suggestions

- The following are suggestions that are given based on the major findings of the study to improve the working of the reliance JIO network.
- The JIO oriented LYF handset has to be made popular among the users of the network as well as other users to make the company popular and increase their turnover by way of improving the advertisement to make the product reach all the corners of the country.

- The network coverage of the JIO network has to be enhanced and infrastructural facilities for the same has to be created for the purpose of increasing the coverage.
- The JIO network has to improve the availability and customer cares services to retain the existing customers and also attract new potential customers towards the network.
- The performance of the JIO network can be increased with the help of enhancing the connectivity and network service availability.

Conclusion

The reliance JIO network has gained the goodwill of the users of the telecom network. It has all the ability to attract users from the other networks with aggressive marketing of the offers and schemes. There are the lot of customers switching over to the JIO network based on the aggressive marketing of the network. The JIO also gave the competitors tough time and made them work with the burden of debt. The JIO network, on the whole, has been able to satisfy the customers and reduce the mobile expenses of the users to an affordable level when compared to the scenario before the entry of the network in the telecom sector. The users of the network are very much satisfied with the data services, call charges and other features of the network. There is also some negativity in the minds of the users on the areas of connectivity and customer care of the network. These are various areas that the network has to concentrate on to improve the goodwill among the users of the network. This will enable to improve the users of the network and also attract the new customers to the network which augurs well for the future of the JIO.

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